

INTEGRATING MULTI-SCALE REMOTE SENSING DATASETS FOR GLOBAL AND REGIONAL LUNAR TERRAIN ANALYSIS. Ankan Majumdar¹ and Deepak Dhingra², ¹Space Planetary and Astronomical Sciences and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, UP 208016, India, (ankanm23@iitk.ac.in), ²Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, UP 208016, India, (deepdpes@gmail.com)

Introduction: The integration of remote sensing datasets across varying spectral and spatial resolutions is essential for resolving ambiguities in lunar surface mineralogy. This study presents a framework for synthesizing hyperspectral data from the Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M³) on Chandrayaan-1 with multispectral data from the Kaguya Multiband Imager (MI) to conduct both global-scale surveys and targeted regional analyses. Our primary objective is to employ a complementary analytical approach by utilizing M³ to identify specific mineralogical exposures and using MI for characterizing various crustal lithologies in detail.

Data and Methods: We apply this integrated approach to investigate Mg-spinel anorthosite, a relatively newly recognized lunar rock type with extensive exposures [1]. Laboratory compositional analyses have demonstrated that the 2-micron absorption band depth of Mg-spinel is strongly correlated and increases rapidly with increasing Fe²⁺ content [2]. By extracting these hyperspectral absorption features from M³ data and coupling them with MI derived abundance maps, we can systematically assess compositional variations across the lunar surface.

We analyzed Mg-spinel exposures at Theophilus crater. Our observations indicate that the spectral character varies significantly across different outcrops within the central peak complex. Figure 1 illustrates various Mg-spinel exposures, which we have grouped into distinct east-west peak zones. To determine the drivers of this spectral variance, we derived the corresponding FeO content (Figure 2) from MI-derived abundance maps for these zones.

Furthermore, representative spectra from four distinct locations (Figure 3) highlight the variance in absorption characteristics across the exposures, specially how the change in FeO content from East to West central peaks manifests in the change in the 2-micron absorption depth.

Conclusion: The observed spectral and compositional variations among the Theophilus Mg-spinel exposures indicate heterogeneous local geology. By directly correlating the 2-micron band characteristics with derived elemental and mineral abundances, we can better assess the degree of heterogeneity and possibly understand the associated causal factors.

References: [1] Dhingra D. et al. (2011) *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 38, L11201. [2] Cloutis E. A. et al. (2004) *Meteoritics & Planet. Sci.*, 39, 545–565.

Figure 1: Mg-Spinel exposures across Theophilus crater, represented over M³ 1489 nm reflectance image

Figure 2: Distribution of FeO wt% across Mg-spinel exposures in Theophilus crater

Figure 3: M³ spectra of 4 different Mg-spinel exposures in Theophilus crater